

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, hydroxyaromatic ketones or β -diketones

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Abstract : Mixed ligand complexes of general formula $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{L}')(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, HL' = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone, pentane-2;4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, TLC, conductances, magnetic moments, IR and electronic spectra.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, cobalt(II), electronic spectra.

In biological systems transition metal ions exist predominantly in the form of different mixed ligand complexes and hence investigations on the synthesis and various structural features of the mixed ligand complexes are increasingly becoming more important¹. Mixed ligand complexes of the type $\text{CoL}_2\text{L}'$, CoLL'_2 and $\text{CoL}_2\text{L}'_2$ have been reported². However, the mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and other ligands have not been reported so far. In the present paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of the mixed

ligand complexes of cobalt(II) of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{L}')(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (1a-d and 2a-c).

Results and discussion

The reactions of cobalt(II) nitrate with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone or 2-hydroxybenzophenone in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (1a-d).

Similarly, the mixed ligand complexes (2a-c) of cobalt(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and β -diketones have been synthesized.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}

The resulting mixed ligand complexes are yellow solids, insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and nitrobenzene but soluble in DMF. Their

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) :			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Conductances ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
					Found (Calcd.)				
					C	H	Co		
1.	[Co(hnp)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	130	30	55.68 (55.82)	4.02 (4.16)	15.01 (15.21)	3.91	13
2.	[Co(hnp)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	177	48	56.59 (56.87)	4.38 (4.52)	14.83 (14.69)	4.78	18
3.	[Co(hnp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	180	55	57.77 (57.98)	4.49 (4.62)	13.98 (14.22)	4.63	10
4.	[Co(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	155	45	62.08 (62.22)	4.03 (4.35)	12.54 (12.72)	4.51	9
5.	[Co(hnp)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	162	69	52.41 (52.61)	4.78 (4.96)	16.38 (16.14)	4.68	36
6.	[Co(hnp)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	145	33	58.97 (59.61)	4.26 (4.49)	13.73 (13.82)	3.87	32
7.	[Co(hnp)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	135	42	63.62 (63.81)	4.35 (4.53)	11.94 (12.04)	4.62	34

characteristics and analyses are recorded in Table 1. Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions in DMF of Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes are low ($9\text{--}36 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, Table 1) indicating their non-electrolytic nature³.

TLC of all the mixed ligand complexes was performed on silica gel G using chloroform petroleum ether (1 : 1) as the mobile phase and the retention times were compared with those of the corresponding bis-complexes. All the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} show single spots with R_f values being intermediate of the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes. This shows that they are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes. The μ_{eff} values of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} (at $\sim 300 \text{ K}$) are in the range $3.87\text{--}4.78 \text{ B.M.}$ suggesting distorted octahedral geometry. Values slightly higher than the spin only value (3.87 B.M.) may be due to orbital contribution⁴.

Strong absorption bands at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and the bands at $\sim 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. In free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone bands at 1660 , 1650 and 1650 cm^{-1} respectively have been assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and in the free β -diketones $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ appears at 1724 cm^{-1} ⁵. Thus the lowering of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in mixed ligand complexes as compared to free ligands supports the coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group to the metal atom⁶. Weak to medium intensity bands observed in the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} in the region $400\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are absent in the free ligands, may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Co-O})$

vibrations. A broad band appears at $3300\text{--}3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of coordinated water molecules⁷. Presence of two coordinated water molecules has been confirmed by thermogravimetric analysis of similar mixed ligand complexes [Co(sal)(bzac)(H₂O)₂] and [Co(hap)(hpp)(H₂O)₂] reported earlier from our laboratories⁸.

The electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded in the range $300\text{--}800 \text{ nm}$. Relatively intense bands are observed at ~ 400 and $\sim 500 \text{ nm}$ which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions respectively. A band at 320 nm is assigned to charge transfer (LMCT). Literature reports three bands at 480 , 380 and 280 nm due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, charge transfer and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively in the mixed ligand complexes of the type $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2(\text{boz})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2(\text{btz})_2$ (where $\text{boz} = \text{benzoxazole}$ and $\text{btz} = \text{benzothiazole}$).

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka), benzoylacetone (Fluka) and dibenzoylmethane (Sisco-Chem) were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (Boehringer), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka), 2-hydroxybenzophenone (Aldrich), acetylacetone (K. Light) and ethanol were purified by distillation. $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) used was of A.R. grade.

To a solution of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4.78 mmol , 1.394

g in ~10 mL ethanol) an ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde (4.78 mmol, 0.824 g) was added with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. The pH, monitored with a pH paper of the mixture was raised to 6.0 by adding 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 4–5 h. The solid that separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Cobalt was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration using xylene orange as indicator¹⁰. TLC of the complexes was performed on silica gel G using chloroform ether (1 : 1) as the mobile phase and the spots on the TLC plates were detected by iodine vapours. Specific conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMF were measured at room temperature on a Systronics conductivity meter-304. Magnetic moments were measured on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer.

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